

Self-growing Robots Inspired by Plants

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Abstract—The ability of plants to explore the environment by adding cells at their tip has inspired a new generation of robots that move by growing. This work describes a robot growing by additive manufacturing. The system has a 3D printer-like mechanism and uses a thermoplastic material to build its body, adapting its shape according to environmental constraints and demanded tasks. Applications of such systems can span from environmental monitoring, archeology, excavation devices or pipes construction.

Keywords—growing robots, bioinspiration, exploration

I. INTRODUCTION

The ability of robots to move and interact with the environment is crucial for performing demanding tasks in out-of-factory scenarios (e.g., aerial [1], terrestrial [2], or marine [3] exploration). Animals are since long source of inspiration for the development of different robotic platforms with improved performance and compliance with the surroundings [4]. More recently, plants have been considered as a model in robotics to develop new systems able to explore unstructured environments [5]–[7]. They are efficient colonizers of above- and below-ground habitats, by extending their roots into the soil and expanding shoots and branches in air. This way, they also provide innovative ideas in the artificial world for navigation and exploration solutions in different contexts, both in terms of mechanisms and controls [8]. Both roots and shoots implement strategies of movement and behaviour while minimizing energetic costs, e.g., oscillatory movements in roots might be adopted to improve penetration performance [9]; while climbing plants adopt several alternative adhesive mechanisms and anchoring strategies to take advantage of existing structures and unload their own weight, concentrating most of their energy for maintenance and growth of apical shoots [10].

Motion in plants is mostly a consequence of an indeterminate growth, which occurs for their entire life, and mostly at their apical levels [11]. Growth is a very interesting feature of living beings that can inspire a generation of robots with new and unpredictable abilities of movement. Noteworthy, plants represent an alternative model of movement in robotics, which is not animal-like and muscle-based.

For the first time in robotics, we proposed a new paradigm of movement inspired by the growth of plants and translated this ability in a new generation of self-growing robots that are able to move by adding new material at the apical region while adapting to external conditions [7].

Application fields for such robots span from pipe constructions, agriculture field monitoring and soil exploration, and archaeology, to non-destructive penetration of substrates which might also include organic tissues for medical applications.

II. GROWING ROBOT BY ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

A. Design

The current growing robot implementation is based on Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) technique. A miniaturized 3D printer-like mechanism is integrated in the tip of the robotic root to pull a filament (polylactic acid - PLA), to fuse the thermoplastic material and deposit the filament at the tip level in a circular manner thanks to a rotating plotting mechanism (Fig. 2a) [7]. The extruded material, which is externally melted when passing through a heater inside the deposition head, can thus adhere to the previously deposited layer. The following bonding between layers allows the incremental growth of the robot's tubular body. Internally, the deposition head anchors to the body by means of metallic fingers, whose sharp edges lock their relative rotation while functioning as a leaf spring and permitting the linear sliding of the printing mechanism inside the printed body.

A successful growth is obtained when the system has power sufficient to overcome the friction force generated by the internal fingers and the external axial forces. A straight growth is achieved by the complete revolution of the deposition extruding mechanism, while, to obtain a bending of the system several strategies can be adopted. One strategy account for the deposition of a different number of layers on one side respect to the opposite side of the tubular body, by inverting the deposition direction [7]; a second strategy assumes a continuous deposition of the material, clockwise or anticlockwise, combined with a speed control on the extruder rotation velocity [12]; lastly, the system can passively adapt its path by deforming the melted material when hitting obstacles during the cooling time after extrusion. Demonstrations of the robot growth are presented

Fig. 1. a) 3D printer-like mechanism with (1a) the plotting mechanism, (2a) the extruder, (3a) metallic fingers, (4a) the feeding motor, and (5a) the plotting motor; b) the robot growing in air, with (1b) the sensorized tip and (2b) the tubular body; c) the robot growing in artificial granular soil (POM); d) the robot growing in unstructure environment with sand and rocky obstacles.

in the Supplementary Video.

This way, and similarly to plant roots and shoots, the system can penetrate the soil or explore the surroundings by growing, increasing the mass while the rest of the structure is stationary and the robot morphology adapts to the external environment.

Such features of the system imply the advantage that the localized growth of the tubular structure makes it easier to overcome the resistance to penetration in granular or clayey substrates [13]. In other words, as the system is penetrating the substrate, the only part of the tubular structure that is moving is the one located at the tip, where new annular layers are added - and where there is still a dynamic friction force -, while the rest of the tubular structure remains still.

B. Behavior

The robot integrates a tip with several sensors (such as humidity, temperature, accelerometer and touch) used for monitoring and enabling the autonomous navigation in the environment on the base of a plant-inspired behavior (e.g., water source localization) [14], useful to direct the growth in unstructured environments. The robot can also be remotely controlled by a user, who can define the exact location and intensity of a bending [15], or to adopt a specific path [16] guiding the growth when the robot has the possibility to reconstruct the close surrounding by means of its own perception.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Drilling and excavation of different kinds of soils are performed in many applications, such as for searching water and fossil fuels, geological studies, etc., and for different targets (collection or deposition of materials, simple opening of a passage towards the surface). Although traditional excavating systems have achieved good levels of effectiveness over the years, they still suffer from a few drawbacks, e.g., they at least partially alter, or even destroy, the substrate and may require high energy consumption.

Instead, when moving aboveground other challenges should be faced by autonomous systems navigating in unstructured environments, such as power autonomy, overcoming voids, rough or vertical surfaces and narrow spaces; requirements that are only partially addressed by the current state of the art.

Starting from very seminal works [17], [18], we are considering plants as source of inspiration for the development of a new paradigm of motion in robotics grounded on the growth ability of these organisms, and implemented in robotic solutions through additive manufacturing approaches. The robot here presented can perform non-destructive penetration through a wide range of substrates, both incoherent and coherent, including artificial soil, air, sand and move among rocks. It forms a hollow tubular structure during the growth process, and this way it creates a channel that might be exploited for the passage of other monitoring devices, water, drugs, energy or other facilities, and as connecting channel to overcome voids.

The inspiration from plants, together with the moving-by-growing strategy, are alternative approaches already gaining strong interest all around the world, and can generate new, unexplored abilities in robots, which can better adapt to external, unstructured conditions, move purposively, effectively and efficiently, with minimum impact on the surrounding environment.

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